

SPECIFIC PROBLEMS OF FORMING A MANAGEMENT STUDENT TEAM AND LEADERSHIP TEAM.

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Annotation: This article describes how to identify and form leadership in a student group, how to properly manage a team. It is revealed that it is necessary to manage the members of the team taking into account their unique character traits, depending on their spiritual worldviews.

Keyword: Group, team, leader, culture, culture, tolerance, component, team, social factors, leadership skills, functional skills, interpersonal skills.

Today, in the era of rapid development of technology, science, and technology, it is very important for people to unite as a team, to move as a group, to unite and cooperate with people with clear goals. It is obvious that a person joins groups in self-realization. Within the group, he interacts with people and can evaluate himself as an individual. A group is understood as a team made up of several people. The student group is, on the one hand, a conditional social group, and on the other hand, it is one of the groups that, under the influence of the dynamics of development, this group should become a real group and community. Normally, from "We are students" to "We are a team" or "We are a team". Then there will be not only unity, but also cases of knowing oneself as different from others will be taken into account. Then they begin to understand their differences from other groups and produce their own value systems, norms and rules, and then the system of "Us" and "Them" is created. It follows that the group of students is such a group that unites them on the basis of a common goal and being together, and the existence of cause and effect is shown. This is the basis for turning the group into a team.

The answer to the question of whether there is an environment for the development of leadership skills in a student group should be started by studying the motivation for joining the group. That is, before becoming a member of the group, we need to study the applicant's needs and subjective meaning. If we can observe how each group, especially the initially conditional groups, turn into a real group and community, we can slowly observe the dynamics of change in the motives of people joining groups in the table. It is possible to determine the dynamic state of the transition of a group to a collective based on the motives of individuals joining groups. It has been found in social psychological studies that in the event of the emergence of the affiliation motive, there is a high possibility that it will become a team when joining a group. On the one hand, there is a desire for intimacy, and on the other hand, there is a fear of intimacy. As a result of the need for security, there is a high probability that the group will become conditional social, and the group will turn into a real group, and from it into a community. The stronger the group, the more peaceful and calm the individuals feel. It is possible to observe that a group united by the need for comparison becomes a conditional social group. When others evaluate the group's activity, it changes. A leader can influence this change. A group united by the need for success becomes a

conditional, voluntary team as a result of respect and mutual respect. As a result of the desire for self-esteem, it turns into a group, and it is determined that the evaluation and support of the activity form the basis of this group. According to the analysis, the influence of the group on the individual in the team and in the group is legal. The behavior of the individual is related to the behavior of the members of the team. Taking into account this law, there are social and psychological factors necessary for the development of individual leadership skills in the student community. That is, it is important and reasonable to recognize the community as a social psychological factor.

In addition, as a social psychological factor in the team, social falsification is the basis for forming the leadership ability of a person. That is, it was observed that a person manifests himself differently under the influence of the audience and team members¹. In particular, based on the experience of M. Ringelmannom, the phenomenon of social laziness was identified as a social psychological factor. That is, when the number of groups increases, the activity result decreases.

So, if there are good conditions for the satisfaction of needs in the student community, it is clear that the number of leaders will increase, besides, these leadership skills will increase based on social facilitation. When a task and a problem situation arise, the ability of leaders to exert their influence decreases when "social laziness" occurs. Then simple situations are performed poorly, difficult situations that require emotional stress are performed well by real leaders. According to the research of D. Jackson and K. Williams, a person who knows that the activities of team members are individually positively evaluated performs simple tasks well, but complex situations are performed well when evaluated collectively.

The conclusion that follows: the inclusion of a person in a team leads to a modification of his behavior. Then it is clear that the ability to lead is manifested especially in those who are freed from social laziness.

It is necessary to take into account the characteristics of group behavior and the impact on the group in order to improve the group's effectiveness when forming leadership skills in the student team. It follows that the student community is an organizational form of collective management. Collective management at the institute is based on the process of empowerment as one of the forms of collective management, which is implemented through the creation and use of student teams. Almost all organizations assign responsibility to managers at various levels for a wider range of tasks than they can handle individually. Based on the distribution of responsibility, managers create one or another form of collective management (D.F. Woodcock, M.V. Francis, 1991). In successful management groups, decisions are developed and made directly by the group, and the role of the administrator is to create the necessary conditions, define the limits of the decision and give the necessary advice in difficult situations.

The team has complementary skills that share common approaches to realizing these goals, values, and joint activities; able to change the ratio of functional roles, assuming responsibility for the final results (capable of performing any roles within the group); a small number of people (often 5 or 7, rarely 15 or 20) who mutually identify themselves and their partner as belonging to this group (society). A student team is a group of students who work

¹Sergeev A.M. Organizational behavior. Economics and management. M. ASADEMA. 2005. b. 120

together on problems or tasks related to a specific field at a certain time. So, if the official group of students consists of 45 students, it can have several teams. No group becomes a community until it considers itself a community (T.Yu. Bazarov, 2021).

The essence of the team is the obligation for all its members (Katzenbash, Sit, 1993). It is important that each member of the team has a goal that they believe in and that it should consist of specific tasks - achievement, first place or progress. T. Yu. Bazarov, V. M. Karimova, R.I.Sunnatova, K.A.Kodirova, N.S.Safayev. Team accountability is the commitment and trust-based commitment of effective teams. Mutual accountability cannot be forced, but when a team shares a common mission, goal, and approach, mutual accountability becomes a natural quality of content. There is a ground for the development of necessary skills in the student body: 1) functional skills (analysis); 2) solving problems and making decisions; 3) interpersonal skills. After the emergence of a student team from a group of students, it is necessary to identify and study the factors that affect the emergence of a team as an organizational form of collective management. It is clear that each team performs a similar task (T.Yu. Bazarov, 2021). So, we should take into account that the student body is participating in the study process. In addition, they perform various tasks in spiritual and educational work and in acquiring a profession, individually or in groups (seminars, lectures). The relationship of the organization of the team with the characteristics of the external organizational environment that interacts with each other. So, on the one hand, there is a team (group of students) and the external environment (faculty, departments), and on the other hand, the specific organizational and cultural context of the group. In team management, the organizational cultural context of the team is mainly defined as separate internal and external conditions. An analysis of the organizational-cultural context of the existence of the student community is presented "Organizational-cultural external and internal context of the existence of the student community". These contexts are extracted from Oldham D. Studies. The formation process of the team (students from the official group) is its internal cultural context. That is, the formation process of its subculture. So, the formation of the student community is related to its subculture. It is necessary to take into account the faculty and direction of the higher educational institution where the students are studying. The purpose of the analysis of subculture forms is to identify the subculture characteristic of the student community. Based on the subculture of the group, the type of joint activity forms the organizational cultural context and the type of leader. T. Yu. Based on the social psychological research conducted under the leadership of Bazarov, it was noted that four main forms of subculture were distinguished: "enterprise", "malicious group", "circle", "community". cultural external and internal context" The level of formality required in the implementation of the organizational contextualization of the existence of the student community is obliged to comply with community norms accepted and shared by all participants. The competence of the main governing bodies in managing the team's activities, the level of obedience and initiative of subordinates are used in the methods of distribution of power. The complexity of the system of the outside world was observed in the student team. To ensure this, importance is attached to the form, agenda, personal characteristics, and the organization and cohesion of the team members is the cultural context of the existence of the student body. The quality of control systems, the presence of rules and operating principles, or emphasizing only the importance of results, specific methods of organizing and managing team cooperation (team processes-coordination, communication, conflict resolution and

decision-making, establishing external relations, etc.) activity on). The level of uncertainty of the control system in the student body was determined. It was found that the thoroughness of work planning is related to the organization of the distribution of roles. It has been determined that stress can occur in the student community, like other communities, depending on the period of work planning. We present the analysis and description of types of subcultures "Types and main characteristics of subcultures". Subordination of members of the enterprise to its strong leader or commander. The fear of losing one's place in the group makes the group obey the traditional hierarchy. The external boundaries and internal structure of the serious group values the individual. The leader has full power. Defines group rules. Control is carried out by the leader. He has the last vote in making decisions. Very stable group culture with quick decision-making. It is determined by the position of the subject in the hierarchy within the group. In the subculture of "evil-minded group", the members of the group completely obey the leader without having their own opinion. The influence of the leader is strong. The group does not have a serious internal structure. A visionary leader leads by allocating internal resources. A visionary leader leads, controls, and makes 100% decisions when making decisions. A circle is determined by standardization and formalization in the form of a single concern subculture. It is governed by rules and regulations. The source of influence is status. Variable has uncertain boundaries; The group splits in crisis. Group members think about their own interests, there is internal competition. A leader brings together transactional experts. Control is related to personal responsibility. Individual creativity corresponding to the vision of the leader, mobility in setting new goals and developing projects, being ready for innovations. Individual interest is above the interest of the group. Community subculture features, open discussion of problems is a good reflection of information. Activity issues and goals change depending on the situation. The main goal is to achieve a clear result. Relationships are based on the principles of interdependence. Leadership is based on contacts and cooperation, support. Management organizes cooperation. Goals are set individually and strategies are developed. Management and control are optimal. The leader is flexible and confident in himself and the members. They pay attention to the professionalism and competence of the team, not depending on its position. In conclusion, it is worth saying that each type of team has its own characteristics. On the one hand, it is caused by the type of leadership, and on the other hand, it is determined that the development of the abilities of the organizational members of the team is related to the level of professionalism and competence.

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